

The Dimensional Composition and Interpretation of Digital Ethics- A Grounded Theory Study Based on Existing Literature

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Abstract

This paper employs the grounded theory approach to conduct an in-depth analysis of the dimensional composition of digital ethics and its application in digital societies. Based on journal articles sourced from CNKI (China National Knowledge Infrastructure), the study reveals five core dimensions of digital ethics through qualitative analysis: meta-rules, digital governance order, the public-private boundary in digital societies, rational logic in the digital age, and ethical risks. The research suggests that the development of digital ethics should facilitate the free flow of information and knowledge sharing, and establish a digital community to promote overall social progress. The study points out that the level of institutionalization of norms is crucial in determining the ethical state of digital societies, and there exist differences in the level of institutionalization of digital ethics across different regions. Therefore, this paper advocates for the construction of an inclusive digital ethics framework that accommodates the needs and expectations of diverse societies.

Keywords: Digital Ethics, Dimensional Composition, Grounded Theory, Diverse Societies.

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